

Removing antibiotics from watercourses by surface immobilization of TiO₂ nanoparticles on poly(vinylidene fluoride) membranes by recrystallization under pressure

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Abstract

The increasing presence of antibiotics in wastewater, a serious risk to public health and the environment, can lead to the generation of antibiotic-resistant bacteria and disturb the ecological balance. Among the possible solutions are photocatalytic mechanisms, which are not based on the absorption/adsorption of the contaminant and so avoid the need for further elimination or destruction; the contaminants are instead directly inactivated by breaking down their molecular structure in a simple and economical process. Although titanium dioxide (TiO₂) has been widely explored for this purpose, the particles need to be chemically attached to the support, which means they can be inactivated, which raises the cost and complexity of the procedure.

Our approach is based on immobilizing TiO₂ in a non-solvent induced phase separation poly(vinylidene fluoride) (PVDF) membrane by means of mechanical compression. Both the non-solvent induced phase separation and mechanical compression techniques are widely used in industrial settings due to their simple, inexpensive and sequential implementation, while PVDF-based supports use their high degree of stability to resist the photocatalytic action of TiO₂ free radicals.

PVDF/TiO₂ membranes degraded 77 % of tetracycline, 56 % of ciprofloxacin and 24 % of metronidazole from respective solutions after 4 h of UV exposure and maintained their photocatalytic activity unaltered for up to 4 consecutive cycles. The degradation kinetics were linear in the 0.5 to 2.5 mg/L range, while the membranes had a large surface area with 89 % of exposed TiO₂, 80 % UV transparency between 360 - 380 nm, and 62 % of PVDF polar structures to prevent fouling.

Introduction

The presence of emerging contaminants in aquatic environments has raised growing concerns due to their detection in extremely low concentrations (ng L⁻¹ to µg L⁻¹) in both wastewater and drinking water [1, 2].

This broad category includes pharmaceuticals, pesticides, endocrine disruptors and different compounds found in personal care products [3, 4]. Although their long-term environmental impact remains uncertain, they can pose potential risks to human health and ecosystems. Of these contaminants, pharmaceutical residues are particularly concerning due to their persistent release into water bodies [5,6]. Medications enter wastewater primarily through household sewage systems [7]. Since standard wastewater treatment processes do not effectively remove these substances, they eventually contaminate surface water, ground water and even drinking water supplies. As a biological contaminant, antibiotic resistance genes have also been found in stormwater runoff at levels comparable to wastewater effluent [8] and as antibiotic resistance is the leading

cause of death around the world it now represents a significant threat to human health [9].

Advanced oxidation processes (AOPs) are among the methods of eliminating antibiotics that are attracting a great deal of interest [10–12]. These processes generate highly oxidative hydroxyl radicals that react non-selectively with pollutants by oxidizing and finally converting them into inert species [13]. Photocatalysis is one of the most widely used of these methods, since it is suitable for decontaminating river courses, among other applications [14]. The basic semiconductor reaction process of generating photocatalytic radicals begins by the absorption of a photon with a certain energy, higher than that of the band gap of the semiconductor, which causes an electron (e⁻) in the conduction band and a hole (h⁺) in the valence band. The reaction of the hole with a water molecule produces a hydroxyl radical (•OH), which can oxidize a contaminant molecule, while the h⁺ itself can degrade the organic contaminant. On the other hand, the e⁻ in the valence band, in contact with an O₂ molecule, can form a radical superoxide (O₂ •⁻). However, electron–hole pairs tend to rapidly recombine, thus limiting the effectiveness of the process [13,15].

TiO₂ is the most widely used photocatalyst because of its good photocatalytic activity, good chemical stability, low toxicity and low cost. An aqueous suspension of TiO₂ nanoparticles has demonstrated its ability to degrade drugs under the action of UV light [16–18]. Although the TiO₂ 3.12 eV bandgap makes it able to absorb light in the UV range it has little activity under sunlight, while the high recombination of electron-hole pairs is another of its drawbacks [15,19].

Although it is highly effective due to its large specific contact surface between the molecule to be degraded and the reactive species generated by photocatalysis, the dispersion of TiO₂ nanoparticles in the aqueous medium containing the organic contaminant introduces the serious problem of eliminating nanoparticles from the aqueous medium. It is therefore very important to develop systems to immobilize nano particles above 10 μm in: i) carriers, which can be collected more easily, ii) on flat membranes on which the aqueous medium circulates, or iii) on porous membranes through which the aqueous medium flows. Polymers are good candidates as scaffolds, while nanocomposite membranes have been developed with synthetic polymer matrices, including poly (ethylene) (PE) [10], poly(vinyl alcohol) (PVA) [11], polymethacrylates [12–17], poly(vinylidene fluoride) (PVDF) [9,18–21], polyamides [22], and also conductive polymers such as poly(aniline) (PANI) [23,24] and natural polymers such as chitosan [25,26], cellulose or cotton [27].

As much of the TiO₂ nanoparticles' effectiveness is lost when they are mixed with the polymer matrix, since many of them do not break the surface, it is usually preferred to explore methods of immobilizing the surface nanoparticles, although a high degree of adhesion must be ensured to prevent the particles detaching from the surface. Another important factor to consider is polymer matrix degradation by the generated reactive species and by the direct effect of UV radiation. In this regard, PVDF has a high resistance to chemicals and UV radiation [20,21], while nanocomposites of PVDF copolymers and TiO₂ nano particles have been shown to be effective in decontaminating a variety of organic molecules such as ibuprofen, ciprofloxacin [21], venlafaxine or metoprolol [22]. The PVDF's inert nature and high chemical, thermal and ionization resistance make them able to withstand renewal processes to decompose adsorbed components while maintaining the support's integrity [23,28,29].

Due to its excellent overall strength and inertness, PVDF is the material most commonly used to produce water filtration membranes [23]. These are usually produced by thermally induced phase separation, TIPS non-solvent induced phase separation and NIPS [24,25]. However, these methods are not without their drawbacks as they produce porous membranes with poor mechanical properties that are not able to produce fully solid and compact PVDF membranes [24,26]. Different studies have modified and combined TiO₂ particles to significantly enhance their degradation efficiency [27,19,30]. However, the simplicity of our proposed approach, which relies exclusively on PVDF and TiO₂, has a significant potential for recyclability [26,27]; both components can be easily separated by density after dissolving the support and recovered to a pure state for reuse, thus avoiding any complex processes [31–33].

Semicrystalline PVDF can crystallize into five main polymorphs, α, β, γ, ε and δ [34,35]. The non-polar α-phase is predominant when the polymer crystallizes from the melt, whereas the polar and electroactive β and γ-phases, are formed from dissolution in certain solvents either by solvent evaporation or by NIPS [34,36]. The β-phase is also formed by the low temperature deformation of a previously membrane crystallized in α-phase

[37,38]. We recently showed that this transition also occurs when a membrane produced by NIPS is under high transversal compressive forces while permitting their deformation on the membrane plane. These recrystallization processes involve the fusion of α crystals induced by mechanical work associated with deformation of the material and subsequent recrystallization under the applied force [39].

In this study we aimed to use this effect to adhere the TiO₂ nano particles onto the surface of a PVDF membrane, which eliminates some of the problems associated with conventional methods used to incorporate TiO₂ nanoparticles into solid substrates. The particles are deposited on the surface of the substrate, increasing their exposure to UV radiation and the subsequent production of radicals, while contact with the medium and the molecules to be degraded is improved. Also, this process does not involve any chemical transformation of the particles for their adhesion, guaranteeing their photocatalytic action. PVDF/TiO₂ membranes produced by solution melting, NIPS and melt compression (combined in the proposed method) are known to maintain the anatase structure of TiO₂ and ensure the conservation of its chemical structure and its photocatalytic behavior, despite its interaction with the PVDF chains [40–42]. It also greatly improves the surface hydrophilicity to maximize contact with the contaminant, increases photocatalytic efficacy and exhibits antibacterial and anti-fouling properties [23,43]. Generating an electric field by piezoelectricity has been proposed to induce the separation of carriers from reactive species by enhancing the photocatalytic effect [44]. Polar orientation in one of the β or γ electroactive phases gives PVDF the piezoelectric properties it lacks in the α -phase [38,40,44].

Although applying TiO₂ particles for the photocatalytic degradation of contaminants is not something new, their physical adhesion to substrates has seldom been explored, especially their attachment through mechanical compression, despite the several advantages this presents: it is affordable since it does not need high temperatures, it is also fast and can be performed sequentially with rollers making it suitable for scaling up to industrial applications. Although some studies have explored the combination and interaction of PVDF and TiO₂ none has directly focused on such a practical and applicable solution as the present proposal. We have managed to combine the main properties of interest, i.e. effective degradation of contaminants, resilience and low maintenance, mechanical and chemical strength, large surface area and UV transparency as well as anti-fouling properties with the simplicity, low cost, and fast production of a method widely applied in industrial settings.

This paper proposes a method of fixing TiO₂ nanoparticles onto a PVDF surface highly crystallized in electroactive phases and the study of their efficiency in degrading three antibiotics in an aqueous solution under UV light. Future studies can be extended to attaching nano particles modified for activity under sunlight or to the degradation of other pollutants. Complementary studies regarding the effect of different experimental and environment parameters on antibiotic photocatalysis would also be of interest and would provide a more in-depth understanding of the support's functionality and predict/explain its behavior under a variety of conditions.

Materials and methods

Materials and reagents

PVDF 6010 was obtained from Solvay (Belgium). Aeroxide[®] Titania P-25 nanoparticles were supplied by EVONIK (Germany). The crystal line structure of these nanoparticles was analysed in [20] and contains both rutile and anatase phases, the latter being the most active in photocatalysis [45,46]. N,N-dimethylformamide (DMF) 99 % and absolute ethanol was supplied by Scharlab (Spain). Tested antibiotics ciprofloxacin (CIP) 98 %, tetracycline hydrochloride (TET) and metronidazole (MET) were obtained from Sigma-Aldrich (Germany). Ultrapure water was obtained by the miliQ(E)[®] water filtration system (Direct-Q 3) Millipore (United States).

Membrane production

Pure PVDF membranes (PVDF NIPS) were obtained by the *Non-Solvent Induced Phase Separation* (NIPS)

technique adapted from the works of Guillot et al. [47,48]. A dissolution of PVDF (20 %) in DMF was prepared and spread out on a glass Petri dish. The sample was then immersed in a pure ethanol bath for 30 min to remove the solvent and solidify the membrane. The glass with the PVDF membrane was then moved to a milliQ® water bath for 24 h to complete the solidification phase, after which the membrane was dried at room temperature.

To obtain the PVDF membranes coated with TiO₂ nanoparticles (PVDF/TiO₂) the desired number of nanoparticles was distributed on the surface of a PVDF NIPS membrane and compressed by a T0–250/20 Gumix (Gumix, United States) hot plates press. The plates were preheated to 110 °C for 1 h and a sandwich of the following materials was assembled: a stainless-steel plate, a Teflon® sheet, PVDF NIPS membrane (14 mm of diameter), TiO₂ nanoparticles, and another Teflon® sheet (the metal and Teflon® were previously preheated to 110 °C). The membrane was subjected to a compression of 110 bar and allowed to cool to room temperature [39]. The samples were then washed in distilled water at 35 rpm for 30 min to remove any TiO₂ that was not stuck to the membrane surface. This protocol produced one membrane surface of pure PVDF (PVDF/TiO₂ A), while the other was coated by TiO₂ nanoparticles (PVDF/TiO₂ B). A PVDF NIPS membrane was also compressed by this protocol without TiO₂ nanoparticles to be used as control (PVDF NIPS PRESS sample).

Membrane characterization

Surface analysis of the macroscopic images of six samples obtained from a digital camera were performed on ImageJ® image analysis software.

Electron microscopy images of sputter-coated samples (Bal-Tec SCD 005, Bal-Tec, Lichstein) were acquired on a Carl Zeiss Ultra 55 (Carl Zeiss, Germany) field emission scanning electron microscope (FESEM) at 2 kV. The samples were fractured after immersion in liquid nitrogen to allow observation of the internal structure.

Images of the PVDF/TiO₂ interface were acquired on a Carl Zeiss Auriga Compact (Carl Zeiss, Germany) scanning electron microscope (SEM) at 2 kV. Cuts were performed with a focused-ion-beam (FIB) accessory applying an Argon beam at 5 µA and 30 kV. Samples were cut and visualized without further processing.

UV transmission was measured in the 360 – 380 nm range in a Cary 60 UV–Vis spectrometer (Agilent, United States) at 360, 370 and 380 nm. To test the sample transmission, they were taped to cover the detector and measurements without a sample were also performed. Five measurements were made on each sample and wavelength to ensure statistical relevance, and the average of each measurement and wave length was used as the final transmission value with the uncovered measurement as reference. A schematic view of the UV spectrometer chamber and the measurement arrangement can be seen in Fig. 1.

Atomic force microscopy (AFM) images were recorded on a Nano scope III (Digital Instruments, United States) placed on an anti-vibration support. A Nanoworld SSS-NCH (Nanoworld, Switzerland) cantilever was used at 45 N/m with 5 nm curvature. Samples were analyzed with a set-point amplitude ratio of 0.7. All the recordings were obtained at room temperature.

Contact angle was calculated from images taken on a contact angle goniometer (Ossila, United Kingdom). A distilled water droplet of 10 µL was dropped from 5 mm onto the sample surface using a micropipette. The water droplet angle was measured on the angle tool of ImageJ® image analysis software; both the left and right angles were measured from 4 images taken from each sample. The values presented were the average of both sides of the 4 measurements. The 4 mg membrane was used as the TiO₂ behavior reference.

Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy (FTIR) spectra were obtained on a Bruker Alpha II (Bruker, USA) in the attenuated total reflectance mode (ATR). Spectra were collected from 400 to 4000 cm⁻¹ after 128 scans with a resolution of 4 cm⁻¹.

Intensity values from the FTIR spectra of specific crystalline peaks can be used to calculate the sample's crystalline phase composition by sequentially applying Eq.-(1) [49–52]. In cases of peak superposition, spectra deconvolution was performed to isolate specific peak intensities.

By applying Eq. (1) both the fractions of electro active phase (EA, the sum of β and γ-phases) and the non-electroactive α-phase were calculated. *FEA* is the percentage of the EA phase, *AEA* and *Aα* is the absorbance peak intensities at 840 and 766 cm⁻¹, respectively. *KEA* and *Kα* are the peak absorbance coefficients at 6.1 and

7.7×10^{-4} cm/mol, respectively.

$$F_{EA} = \frac{A_{EA}}{\left(\frac{K_{EA}}{K_{\alpha}}\right) A_{\alpha} + A_{EA}} \quad (1)$$

By applying Eq. (2) the FEA can then be split into β and γ contributions to allow them to be individually quantified. F_{γ} and F_{EA} are the percentage of the γ and EA phases, A_{β} and A_{γ} are the absorbance peak intensities at 1275 and 1234 cm^{-1} , respectively.

$$F_{\gamma} = F_{EA} \left(\frac{A_{\gamma}}{A_{\gamma} + A_{\beta}} \right) 100 \quad (2)$$

Fig. 1. Schematic view of the UV–Vis spectrometer internal chamber, including the corresponding sample location, experimental arrangement and UV transparency experimental parameters.

Photocatalysis degradation

A custom membrane holder (Fig. 2) designed on Autodesk Tinker cad® was printed with a poly(lactic acid) PLA HD filament (Winkle, Spain) without additives on a Prusa i3 Mk3 printer (Prusa Research, Czechia). Membranes were cut into 5 cm^2 disks and fixed by the membrane holder (Fig. 2) to the bottom of a beaker filled with 50 mL of aqueous solutions of CIP, tetracycline or metronidazole at 2.5 mg/L. The distance from the membrane to the water surface was 14 mm at the beginning of the experiment. To reach the adsorption–desorption equilibrium, the solutions and the membranes were kept in the dark under stirring for 30 min. The incident radiation over the sample, measured with a lux meter, was around 0.3 $\mu\text{W}/\text{cm}^2$.

The antibiotic solution absorbance was measured to analyze the antibiotic’s photocatalytic degradation as a function of time on a Victor3 UV_Vis 1420 multilabel counter spectrophotometer (Perkin Elmer, USA), considering the intensity of the main absorption peak at 380 nm. Three equal membrane disks were measured to obtain the mean value and the standard deviation (SD) expressed as the mean \pm SD.

Fig. 2. Digital rendering of the membrane holder. Disassembled (left) and assembled with the membrane (orange circle) in position (right). Large quadrangles are in cm.

Antibiotic degradation kinetics

A Langmuir-Hinshelwood model was fitted to calculate the kinetics of the antibiotic degradation process by the TiO₂'s photocatalytic activity [46,53]. This model can be expressed as a pseudo-first-order reaction [20,54] by applying Eq. (3), where k is the pseudo-first order rate constant of the degradation process, C_0 and C are the initial and measured solute concentrations, respectively, and T is the time in minutes.

$$\ln\left(\frac{C}{C_0}\right) = -kT \quad (3)$$

Results and discussion

Microstructure

To obtain the membranes the NIPS procedure is applied, in which the PVDF solution in DMF is spread on a glass Petri dish and the solvent is extracted with ethanol as non-solvent; a porous membrane is produced in accordance with [24,55]. The microstructure of these PVDF NIPS membranes had highly porous submicrometric internal and external structures (Figs. 3c and 2d respectively). The thickness of the membranes obtained before compression was around 700 μm (Fig. 3b), in agreement with [47,48].

The compression process does not melt the PVDF, as the temperature used (110 °C) is significantly lower than the melting temperature of PVDF (172 °C, considered as the maximum of the endothermic melting peak on a differential scanning calorimeter, results not shown) [56]. The compression process extends the sample, producing a transparent membrane (Fig. 3a), doubling its mean diameter (Feret diameter) and reducing its thickness to around 20 μm (Fig. 3f). The pore is completely collapsed both on the surface (Fig. 2e) and in the cross-section (Fig. 2f) of the membrane, as in previous experiments [39]. The mechanical compression of PVDF NIPS membranes and the subsequent compaction of the internal structures also have implications for the mechanical properties; previous studies have reported a 15 to 24-fold higher Young's modulus [39].

To produce the PVDF/TiO₂ membrane, a layer of nanoparticles was distributed over the surface of the original disc. Part of these nano particles remain inside the surface pores and another part forms a layer that completely covers the sample's surface. When compressed in the hot plate press, the deformation of the PVDF sheet drags the surface particles over the whole membrane, although this coating is not homogeneous. Fig. 4a shows a macroscopic image of a representative membrane, in which can be seen the different tones of the white TiO₂ coated areas and the transparent PVDF membranes in the non-coated areas. The precise criteria to distinguish these areas was based on the FTIR spectra (see Section 3.4).

Image analysis revealed that the coated surface depends on the number of nanoparticles initially distributed on the original 14 mm diameter membrane disk. When using 2 mg of nanoparticles, the pressed membrane has a coated surface of $72 \pm 3 \%$; adding 4 mg the covered area is $84 \pm 1 \%$, and adding 8 mg it reaches $89 \pm 5 \%$. In the areas with the highest particle surface density, the thickness of the layer of agglomerated nanoparticles is around 1 μm , as can be seen in the cross-section image obtained by the FIB ion cannon at FESEM (Fig. 4e). The compactness of the surface nanoparticles can be seen in the AFM images of both height and phase (Fig. 3b and 3c respectively) and in the FESEM image (Fig. 4d).

Transmission of UV radiation

In order to verify the high transparency to the UV radiation of the PVDF NIPS PRESS membranes, treated by mechanical compression, a transmission test was carried out in the wavelength range 360 to 380 nm, the emission range of lamps used for the excitation of TiO₂ nano particles in photocatalytic experiments.

Transmission measurements were carried out both with and without membranes covering the detector to evaluate the difference in radiation intensity between detected radiation whose difference correlated with the UV transmission/transparency (Supplementary Fig. 1). Both PVDF NIPS and PVDF NIPS PRESS membranes were used (see results in Table 1).

Although PVDF NIPS membranes are opaque to the range of UV radiation used, when they are mechanically compressed their transmission increases to 80 %. This increase also applies to the radiation in the visible range, as can be seen in Fig. 4(a). This transmission in the excitation range of TiO₂ particles allows the radiation to pass through the membrane and excite nanoparticles through it. This provides a wider variety of possible geometries and assemblies in the construction of photocatalysis devices based on TiO₂ nanoparticles and PVDF membranes. The method achieves similar levels of transparency to thermal annealing, demonstrating that two-step post-processing is needed to simultaneously achieve high transparency and electroactive properties.

Fig. 3. (a) Macroscopic image of a PVDF NIPS membrane (left) and a PVDF NIPS PRESS membrane (right); (b) cross section of the PVDF NIPS membrane; (c) and (d) FESEM images of the surface microstructure and the cross section of the PVDF NIPS membrane, respectively; (d) and (e) FESEM images of the surface microstructure and the cross section of the PVDF NIPS PRESS membrane, respectively. The scale bar corresponds to 200 μm in (b), 1 μm in (c), (d), (e) and 2 μm in (f).

Water contact angle

The water contact angle was measured on all the samples. Mechanical compression of the NIPS sample did not cause significant changes in the membrane's wettability when both cases had a contact angle of approximately 90° (Table 2). However, when TiO_2 was present on the surface the wettability mainly increased with an average contact angle of 35° . As expected, the polar nature of the nanoparticles increased membrane hydrophilicity [57,58], a crucial parameter for the photocatalytic behavior, by increasing the contact between the degradable antibiotics and the photocatalytic TiO_2 particle [59–61]. The side without nanoparticles maintained the typical PVDF hydrophobic characteristic, thus preventing it from fouling. Representative images of the sample's wettability can be seen in Supplementary Fig. 2.

The higher SD of the sample containing TiO_2 correlates with the particle distribution shown in Fig. 4a. The density of adhered particles, the components responsible for hydrophilic behavior, cause a variation in the contact angle, seen as lighter and darker regions.

Fig. 4. (a) Macroscopic image of a PVDF membrane coated with TiO_2 nanoparticles, showing the heterogeneity of the distribution of nanoparticles, with regions of higher or lower density of nanoparticles. The scale shown at the left is in mm; (b) and (c) show the aggregates of nanoparticles in the AFM height and phase images, taken in the area of highest TiO_2 density. The image size corresponds to $1 \times 1 \mu\text{m}$; (d) FESEM image of the area of highest density of TiO_2 ; (e) cut of the surface of the sample made with an ion cannon, showing a thickness of approximately $1 \mu\text{m}$ for the TiO_2 layer. The scale bar in (d) and (e) corresponds to $1 \mu\text{m}$.

Table 1

Transmission of UV radiation between 360–380 nm through the PVDF NIPS and PVDF NIPS PRESS membranes.

Sample	Transmission (%)
Without membrane	102
PVDF NIPS	1
PVDF NIPS PRESS	80

Table 2

Water contact angle of the PVDF NIPS and PVDF NIPS PRESS membranes.

Sample	Water contact angle
PVDF NIPS	90° ± 1
PVDF NIPS PRESS	90° ± 1
PVDF NIPS PRESS TiO ₂	35° ± 4

Crystalline phases

The effect of the sample deformation at 110 °C (below its melting temperature) on the PVDF crystal phase distribution was studied by FTIR. Although other techniques are available, FTIR was chosen as it is the most commonly used technique for the evaluation of PVDF crystal phases [49,62] and can also give further information on possible molecular interactions or alterations to the molecular structure [62,63]. Fig. 5 shows the spectra of the original sample (PVDF NIPS) and the pressed membrane (PVDF/TiO₂).

PVDF specific peaks can be seen in the FTIR spectra (Table 3), thus confirming the identity of the polymer used. The lack of additional peaks between the unprocessed PVDF and the remaining samples and among the samples themselves is an indicator that no chemical bonding took place between the PVDF and the TiO₂, confirming that our method is based on mechanical immobilization. Minimal peak displacements were observed after adding TiO₂, confirming a certain degree of interaction between the two components [64–66]. The addition of charged particles is known to interact with PVDF chains, as confirmed by Table 4 [67,68].

In the unprocessed PVDF sample with an unknown thermal history, PVDF is predominantly present in its α -phase (close to 100 %) as demonstrated by the presence and intensity of α -phase peaks and the absence of those associated with the electroactive phases β and γ (Fig. 5). In the PVDF NIPS membrane, the crystallization from the DMF solution induced by the non-solvent reduces the α -phase fraction to 53 % while β and γ electroactive phases increase to 47 % (Table 4), findings in good agreement with the results obtained in [48].

After mechanical compression of the PVDF NIPS membrane, the fraction of electroactive phases still increases, as shown by the growth of the corresponding peaks. e.g. the 839 cm⁻¹ peak in Fig. 5, accompanied by a large reduction in the non-electroactive phase peaks. This shows that the post-processing by mechanical compression promotes the melting of α -phase crystals due to the mechanical force transmitted to the material during extreme deformation under the applied compression forces and re-crystallization in the electroactive structures [39]. We also consider that this melting and recrystallization process can be attributed to the TiO₂ nanoparticles strongly adhering to the surface.

The PVDF NIPS membrane already had a high content of β and γ -phases, as confirmed by comparing the intensity of the peaks at 839 cm⁻¹ of the PVDF NIPS membrane with a membrane crystallized from the melt. When the sample is deformed during compression, the β -phase fraction increases significantly in relation to the γ -phase, as seen when analyzing the behavior of the 1270 cm⁻¹ peak characteristic of the β -phase, to which the γ -phase does not contribute (Table 4). The FTIR spectrum of the PVDF/TiO₂ membrane side coated with TiO₂ nano particles shows absorption peaks due to TiO₂, overlapping with the region between 600 and 800 cm⁻¹ of the PVDF spectrum (Fig. 5). For this reason, the crystal phase content of the TiO₂ side could not be calculated, although the comparison of the size and shape of the peaks in the 1200 to 1300 cm⁻¹ region confirms that contact with the nanoparticles has an additional effect on the recrystallization of electroactive structures under compression (Supplementary Fig. 3). This effect has not been previously reported, although increased electroactive phases have been found when mixed with TiO₂, which further strengthens the idea of PVDF re-crystallization under mechanical loading.

Fig. 5. FTIR spectra of the PVDF powder, the PVDF NIPS membrane, and the two sides of the PVDF/TiO₂ membrane PVDF NIPS PRESS membrane without TiO₂ particles, and PVDF/TiO₂ membrane with TiO₂ particles measuring the side that does not contain the particles (PVDF/TiO₂ A) and the side containing the particles (PVDF/TiO₂ B). The vertical lines mark the peaks associated with the PVDF crystalline phases α , β and γ .

Table 3

Specific peaks of the different crystalline phases of the PVDF [49,51,69].

PVDF crystalline phase	Absorbance frequency (cm ⁻¹)	Chemical group
α	614	CF ₂
	763	CF ₂
	795	CH ₂
	975	CH
β	1276	CF
$\beta + \gamma$	840	CH ₂
γ	1234	CF ₂

Table 4

Independent crystalline phase percentages for the PVDF NIPS, PVDF NIPS PRESS and PVDF TiO₂ samples.

	PVDF NIPS	PVDF NIPS PRESS	PVDF/TiO ₂ A
α	53	31	38
β	18	32	32
γ	29	37	30

Photocatalytic activity

Fig. 5a and 5b show the degradation of a 2.5 mg/L solution of CIP by photocatalysis under UV light for 240 min in terms of the decrease in antibiotic concentration in the solution over time, with reference to the initial concentration C_0 , and in terms of the total mass of antibiotic degraded over time, respectively (raw results available in Supplementary Fig. 5.). The results from membranes with different amounts of TiO₂ nanoparticles (2 mg, 4 mg, and 8 mg) are also shown. The linear correlation between the nanoparticle content and the photocatalytic effect can be seen with no saturation within the time interval of the experiment. The TiO₂ action mechanism on antibiotics under UV illumination has been extensively analysed in the literature [45,70–72]. Silva et al., studied the mechanism and degradation products of CIP by the action of TiO₂ nanoparticles in suspension [73]. The degradation products of CIP when TiO₂ nanoparticles are immobilized on different substrates have also been studied in detail [74–76,70].

There are wide variations in the results obtained in the literature on the degradation of CIP by photocatalysis with TiO₂ particles. Wang et al. studied the photocatalytic effect of Europium-modified TiO₂ on PVDF membranes and found that the C/C_0 value dropped to 0.85 in 200 min [77]. Salma et al., studied the photocatalysis of CIP with nanoparticles immobilized on glass plates, reaching C/C_0 values of 0.2 at pH7 within 120 min, but higher values of the order of 0.5 at acidic pH [76]. C/C_0 values between 0.85 and 0.6 at 300 min, depending on the nanoparticle content and membrane porosity were found for PVDF/ethylene hexafluoride copolymer composite membranes and gold-modified TiO₂ nanoparticles under UV illumination [78,19].

It is difficult to compare our results with those obtained in other systems in which TiO₂ nanoparticles are immobilized on flat substrates, since much depends on the characteristics of the experimental device: e. g. the UV lamp used, distance to the sample, membrane surface in relation to the volume of antibiotic solution, and others. Degradation kinetics is also affected by parameters such as temperature, pH of the antibiotic solution, the presence of various contaminants in the aqueous solution, or the analysis of natural watercourses.

Fig. 6c shows the effect of the initial concentration of the CIP solution on the photocatalytic activity: the decrease in concentration is proportional to the initial amount of antibiotic, so that no significant differences can be seen in the C/C_0 diagram. This indicates that the kinetics of the degradation process is dominated by the probability of antibiotic molecules reaching the surface coated with TiO₂ and thus by the specific assay conditions.

In order to explore the stability of the membrane coating, a series of PVDF/TiO₂ membranes was subjected to consecutive photocatalysis assays (each one lasting 240 min). Fig. 6d shows that the first four degradation cycles are practically overlapping while the membrane's effectiveness clearly decreases from the fifth cycle onwards.

The reusability of PVDF-based copolymer nanocomposites with TiO₂ nanoparticles was analysed by Teixeira et al., in [20]. The photoactivity of a nanocomposite with 15 % TiO₂ was reduced by 16 % after three uses. Haenel et al. obtained an 8 % loss of activity in phenol degradation in the third reuse of glass beads coated with TiO₂ nanoparticles [79]. Salazar et al., studied the effect of up to 3 cycles of degradation of Norfloxacin and found that C/C_0 after 90 min illuminated with UV increased from 0.35 to 0.55 [19]. Wang et al., found that CIP degradation at 360 min went from C/C_0 0.8 to 0.95 at the fifth reuse [77].

Fig. 6. Photocatalysis results. (a) CIP degradation using membranes with different contents of TiO₂, expressed in terms of concentration in relation to the initial concentration C/C_0 . (b) CIP degradation using membranes with different contents of TiO₂, expressed in terms of percentage of CIP mass eliminated from the solution. (c) CIP degradation of different initial concentrations using membranes with 8 mg of TiO₂, expressed in terms of C/C_0 . (d) CIP degradation in eight consecutive cycles using membranes with 8 mg of TiO₂, expressed in terms of concentration. The solid lines are those of cycles 1, 4, 5 and 8 (e) CIP, TET and MET degradation using membranes with 8 mg of TiO₂ (f) Fit of the pseudo-first order model to the degradation of the different antibiotics.

The loss of photocatalytic activity in TiO₂ nanoparticles immobilized on different substrates is often associated with the loss of nanoparticles during use. Optical inspection of the membranes (Fig. 4a) reveals whiter or more transparent zones due to the higher or lower presence of TiO₂. FTIR analysis revealed TiO₂ peaks in the intense white areas and their absence in the more transparent areas (Supplementary Fig. 2). To define the area fraction covered by nanoparticles, image analysis was performed on six membranes. The six samples were then subjected to wear under a water flow by shaking in a beaker for 72 h at 250 rpm in a magnetic stirrer, after which there was no change in the fraction of coated surface. This suggests that the active area for photocatalysis is stable after membrane use, but the thickness of the coating probably decreases as the cycles are repeated.

The membrane's effectiveness in degrading tetracycline and metronidazole is shown in Fig. 6f, together with the CIP degradation curve. The results show that degradation kinetics varies between different compounds due to their different chemical nature, more or less sensitive to photocatalysis. Photocatalysis is affected by different external factors such as light intensity, pH, temperature and the exposed surface. In particular, pH seriously affects the degradation capacity of degradable molecules via TiO₂ [80]. It is therefore difficult to compare our results with the findings of other studies, since diverse degradation kinetics are found in the literature due to the different parameters which can affect photocatalysis (as well as the photocatalyst used) [70,81]. Some studies did not find degradation differences the antibiotics we used, which either have different rates of degradation or respond differently depending on pH or their ability to interact with the surface of the photocatalyst [82,83]. When comparing the photocatalytic degradation of TET and MET with the data in the literature, something similar occurs to what we have described above for CIP: as the experimental conditions of the different studies vary widely the results are difficult to compare [82,27,84,85].

Kinetics analysis

Fig. 6 shows the linearity of the relationship in Eq. (3) for the different antibiotics. The fit leads to values of $k = 0.0071 \text{ min}^{-1}$ for TET, 0.0030 for ciprofloxacin and 0.0011 for MET. It is difficult to compare these values with others in the literature because the degradation rate depends on a variety of factors, including the UV lamp used, the distance between the lamp and the sample, the membrane surface, the temperature and others. In fact, in the series of samples in this work containing 2, 4 or 8 mg of TiO₂ nanoparticles, the value of k is 0.0009, 0.0016 and 0.0030 cm^{-1} respectively. As a guideline, in the studies by Wang et al., the value of the kinetic constant varies from 0.0004 to 0.0016 cm^{-1} [77]. Zheng et al. studied the effect of the type of UV lamp and reported values of k ranging between 0.0008 and 0.053 cm^{-1} [78].

Conclusions

This paper describes a proposed method of purifying water by immobilizing TiO₂ nanoparticles on PVDF surfaces whose results show it to be highly efficient and straightforward. We confirmed that the TiO₂ particles remain on the surface after agitation in water, ensuring its safe use and without introducing any new contaminants into the water. The procedure effectively fixates the nanoparticles through mechanical compression on a previously formed PVDF membrane, changing its structure from highly porous to completely solid. This procedure can easily be scaled up to the industrial level by replacing the press with a calender, making it suitable for a sequential production procedure. Using PVDF as the substrate ensures good mechanical properties and resistance to abrasion, adverse weather conditions and TiO₂ photo catalytic action. We have shown these membranes to be effective for degrading antibiotics by photocatalysis. The membranes produced exhibited:

- **Completely solid structures**, ensuring good mechanical strength and avoiding the penetration of biomass or contaminants to maintain the membrane's transparency properties
- **80 % UV transparency between 360 and 380 nm**, this means that irradiation can be performed from both sides of the membrane to allow a variety of setups that can be built to suit different needs.
- **Surface composed of 89 % exposed TiO₂**, increased surface area to maximize the contact and exposure of contaminants to the free radicals, thus augmenting the photocatalytic action and the subsequent degradation of the contaminant.
- **Degradation of tetracycline, 77 %, ciprofloxacin, 56 %, and metronidazole, 24 %, after 4 h**, demonstrating a capacity to rapidly degrade a variety of antibiotics, showcasing the polyvalence of the degradation mechanism and providing a single solution to the variety of wastewater contaminants in need of removal.
- **Linear kinetics between 0.5 and 2.5 mg/mL**, No loss of effectiveness or saturation in the concentrations tested, implying a constant degradation ratio for the duration of the experiment and ensuring predictability of the removal and duration of wastewater contaminants.
- **Photocatalytic activity maintained up to 4 consecutive cycles**, demonstrating the reliability and easy

maintenance of the photocatalytic membranes when applied to degrading contaminants, greatly reducing the cost of the treatment and materials.

- **62 % of anti-fouling polar structures**, producing membranes with a surface polar net charge giving natural intrinsic antibacterial and anti-fouling properties for continuous photocatalytic effectiveness and contributing to a long-lasting application requiring little maintenance.

The membranes produced by the above-described method proved effective in degrading the antibiotics tested: due the photocatalytic action method, they would most likely also degrade other antibiotics or pollutants while the method could also be applied to other particles or combination of particles. This proposed system shows promise due to its plasticity, simplicity and effectiveness and should be further explored for water remediation applications.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Luis A. Martins: Writing – original draft, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation. **José Luis Gómez Ribelles:** Writing – review & editing, Validation, Supervision, Resources, Project administration, Methodology, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization. **Joaquín Ródenas-Rochina:** Supervision, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation. **Diana C. Akudolu-Imafidon:** Investigation, Formal analysis. **Roser Sabater i Serra:** Visualization, Validation, Methodology. **José Antonio Gómez-Tejedor:** Supervision, Resources, Methodology. **Senentxu Lanceros-Méndez:** Writing – review & editing, Validation, Supervision, Resources, Project administration, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization. **Isabel Tort-Ausina:** Writing – original draft, Validation, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Data availability

The data used for the production of this manuscript will be available upon request.

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Supplementary material

Supplementary figure 1. UV transmission at different wavenumbers with an unobstructed light pathway, and with the detector covered with an uncompressed and compressed PVDF NIPS film.

Supplementary figure 2. Water droplet deposited on the surface of the neat samples, NIPS PVDF, after mechanical compression, PVDF NIPS PRESS, and the mechanically compressed membranes with 4 mg of TiO₂ on its surface, PVDF NIPS TiO₂ (top to bottom).

Supplementary figure 3. FTIR spectra of the different zones of the mechanically compressed PVDF film coated with TiO₂.

Supplementary figure 4. FTIR spectra of the electroactive phase peaks.

Supplementary figure 5. Raw photocatalysis results expressed as absorbance. (a) Degradation of the CIP using membranes with different contents of TiO₂. (b) Degradation of different initial concentrations of CIP using membranes with 8 mg of TiO₂. (c) Degradation of CIP in eight consecutive cycles using membranes with 8 mg of TiO₂. The solid lines correspond to cycles 1, 4, 5 and 8 (d) Degradation of CIP, TET and MET using membranes with 8 mg of TiO₂.